

Abstract: SpillsWatch, a Science Gateway for Oil Spill Access, Analysis and Visualization

S. Casagrande Cecchin¹, G. Tabarelli de Fatis¹, T. M. Arabi¹, M. Robol¹, S. Fiore^{1*}

¹Department of Information Engineering and Computer Science, University of Trento, Trento, Italy
[*sandro.fiore@unitn.it](mailto:sandro.fiore@unitn.it)

Oil is one of the most used resources in many industry sectors. Known also as the 'black gold', it quickly became a hub of the global economy, thanks to its chemical properties and energy production potential. Meanwhile, oil became a major driver of marine pollution. The oil used as a major energy resource has led to a need for extraction, transportation, storage and quality checks. Accidents in this production chain are frequent and dangerous: shipwrecks, vulnerable tankers, pipeline failures, and offshore oil drilling operations. Not only: oil that does not meet quality standards is often intentionally released in the sea and since this happens trying to evade controls, detection becomes even harder. The crucial point is that oil can cause severe damages, contaminating the water and harming its fauna, thus severely impacting the entire marine ecosystem. Given the global scale of this kind of transportation, along with its extremely high risk, it is crucial to keep close track of oil routes, in order to detect any possible spills. Upon spills detection, immediate priorities include not only initiating cleanup efforts but also understanding their behavior over time: forecasting and evaluation models are primary in risk prevention and assessment, particularly in proximity to populated areas. Of course this is not simple: various factors must be considered and lots of detailed data is required to effectively model and predict the complex and dynamic spills nature. From this idea, in the context of the EU project iMagine [1], we have developed SpillsWatch [2], a Science Gateway for oil spill access, analysis and visualization. It integrates a catalog with a dataset including hundreds of oil spills [3] and simulated data from Medslik-II [4], a freely available oil transport and transformation community model which simulates the transport of the surface slick governed by the water currents and by the wind. The SpillsWatch Science Gateway provides a visual representation of different spills included in the available data set on a geographical map. Starting from a global heatmap, users can explore each spill in detail either through a visual search or by referring to a catalog. SpillsWatch makes use of an Elasticsearch database engine to index observation data and retrieve information to users. A particularly intriguing feature of the application is the Oil Spill Analysis, which showcases all spills that have undergone an oil spill simulation. Users can track the progression of each spill on an hourly basis over a span of three days (see Figure below). The unique value of the SpillsWatch Science Gateway is the delivery of a comprehensive set of functionalities integrating both simulated and observed data and offered to the end users through a very attractive and easy-to-use UI.

References

- [1] iMagine project: <https://www.imagine-ai.eu/>
- [2] SpillsWatch website: <http://wa.imagine.disi.unitn.it/ocean>
- [3] Segmented oil spills dataset: <https://zenodo.org/records/11354663>
- [4] Medslik-II project website: <https://www.cmcc.it/models/medslik-ii>